

Building a French Revolution Narrative from Wikidata

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Abstract

Historical reconstructions can help us better understand important events. This is essential for bettering our knowledge on specific topics and this enables us to build coherent sequences of information. Knowledge graphs like Wikidata contain information about generic knowledge that includes historical events, but the information is often entity-centric rather than event-centric. This makes the analysis and understanding of events related to a same topic harder, since it is less easily accessible. In this demonstration paper, we developed a system to build a timeline about the French Revolution in the form of a graph of a sequence of events, also called a narrative in this work. The system comes with an interface, where a user can first select the types of events to be retrieved, and is then walked through the steps of the system. The output of the system is a timeline of the French Revolution.

1. Introduction

We constantly create narratives to provide explanations or justifications for why and how something happens. This capability of creating such narratives is even suggested to be part of what makes us human [1, 2]. AI systems able to create narratives could therefore help in the realisation of human-centric systems. In this demonstration paper, we present a system that can build a timeline of the French Revolution by exploring Wikidata. The system takes the user's inputs to select nodes in Wikidata, walks the users through the different steps and outputs a timeline.

The system presented in this demonstration paper builds a narrative in the form of a graph. A narrative is defined here as a sequence of events. The main novelty of the paper is a system that walks the user through the different steps of the process and lets the user choose the events to include for the narrative. Earlier systems could let the user navigate through events and entities without a final timeline output [3], or could build the timeline without interacting with the user, for example by retrieving most significant events for a biography description [4].

2. Related Work

A narrative is one way to understand or explain a series of related events. In this work, a narrative is technically defined as a sequence of events in the form of a graph. A narrative in this context is thus a type of knowledge graph. Therefore, our work is related to narratives and to how events are structurally represented, especially in event knowledge graphs structures. The output of our system is a timeline generated from a knowledge graph, hence our work is also related to timeline generation from knowledge bases. We describe the aforementioned research domains in this section.

Narratives are a means for better understanding how a situation unfolds over time. The events are the atomic concepts underlying these narratives. Towards formally defining such structures, Bartalesi and Meghini [5] for example propose to define formal components of narratives using event calculus theory [6].

From a resource perspective, the closest to our work would be event knowledge graphs that focus on describing events and links between them. Guan et al. [7] survey event knowledge graphs from four different perspectives: history, ontology, instance and application. More recent research has focused on providing better access to semantic structured data about events, and has emphasised the need to have such event-centric information for applications such as timeline generation or history reconstruction. Available resources now include (i) EventKG [8] built from generic knowledge graphs, (ii) a knowledge graph built from textual news data [9] (iii) a knowledge graph built from a Sherlock Holmes novel [10] (iv) semantic data for cultural heritage [11] and (v) GDELT [12] and ICEWS [13].

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From an application perspective, the closest to our work would be systems that use knowledge bases for timeline or hypothesis generation. The aim of such systems is to help a user understand better one topic. For quality, Althoff et al. [14] define three criteria for a timeline quality: relevance, temporally diverse and content diverse. For applications, Metilli et al. [4] use Wikidata to build biographies, e.g. Dante’s one. Kroll et al. [15] furthermore build narratives as hypotheses on top of different knowledge bases, with an application in the biomedical domain.

3. Demonstrator Features

Extracting a French Revolution Narrative Graph from Wikidata and Wikipedia

What

This web interface enables to collect data from Wikidata and Wikipedia to build narratives. The focus is on the French Revolution.

Why

This demo enables a user and a machine to interact to build a narrative timeline of the French Revolution. The user’s inputs help the machine select the nodes to extract for the narrative, whereas the timeline output can enhance the reader’s knowledge about this historical topic.

How

To run this demo entirely, you should go to every Navigation page (see left column menu) in order:

1. **Event Collection.** the user can select the paths to extract the events from
2. **Wikidata Enrichment.** retrieving outgoing nodes of each event from Wikidata
3. **Link Extraction.** for each event that has a pointer to a Wikipedia page, the infobox information is retrieved if there is any. This step might take a bit longer.
4. **Build Network.** from the data collected, RDF triples are constructed
5. **Display Network.** Visualisation of the French Revolution narrative as a timeline

Figure 1: Home page of the application.

In the demonstration system, the user is walked through the different steps to build a narrative graph: 1) Collect events from Wikidata and select paths to extract nodes from 2) Extract features from Wikidata 3) Extract additional information from Wikipedia info boxes 4) Convert the data into RDF triples compatible with the Simple Event Model 5) Display the narrative graph as a timeline,

with a description of each event as well as event type and participants. The demonstrator currently outputs a timeline for the French Revolution only, but could be extended to other types of revolutions for instance. The code is publicly available¹.

The backend is written in Python 3.9.4, the interface was developed with Streamlit². Wikidata was accessed through the Wikidata SPARQL endpoint. Figure 1 shows the home page of the demonstrator that explains the purpose of the application and the main steps to extract the timeline.

3.1. Event Collection from Wikidata

The first step to build the timeline is to collect events from Wikidata. In the demonstrator, the user can select a collection of paths to extract events from, depicted in Figure 2. The user can then press the button “Collect events” to query the Wikidata knowledge graph.

Events and links to Wikidata and Wikipedia are stored in the backend, and the user is provided with some additional information, such as the number of events retrieved.

3.2. Extracting narrative features

Once the events have been extracted from Wikidata depending on the user’s input paths, the next step is to extract narrative features for the events. A narrative feature for an event contains information about either a participant, a timestamp, a location, a type of event, or a temporal or causal link to another event. In Section 2. and 3. displayed in Figure 1, the user can press a button to extract these features.

In the demonstrator, the user can see the features that were extracted, as well as some additional statistics on the distribution of the types of features. We found that features extracted from Wikidata contained mostly information about time and location, whereas features extracted from Wikipedia contained more information about participants and causal links.

Features in Wikipedia also contain hyper links to other Wikipedia pages, which can therefore be linked back to Wikidata. We use and retrieve these corresponding Wikidata pages to have consistent URIs for the final graph.

¹ <https://github.com/SonyCSLParis/building-fr-narrative-from-wikidata>

² <https://streamlit.io>

Several types of nodes were taken into account for this pilot:

- <event> part of <French Revolution>
- <French Revolution> has significant event <event>
- <event> is instance of <historical country> and has country <France>

An additional filter was added to extract events in the right time range.

Select the paths that you want to use for event collection:

Choose the types of events you want to retrieve

Choose an option

- <event> part of <revolution>
- <revolution> has significant event <event>
- <event> is instance of <historical country> and has country <>

Please select at least one path.

Collect events

Figure 2: Collecting events from Wikidata

3.3. Building the network

The next step is to build a narrative graph of the French Revolution events and their description, in the form of RDF triples. The rules to convert the extracted features for each event to triples were designed manually. The ontology used is the Simple Event Model [16]. The four main classes of this model are: `sem:Event` (what), `sem:Actor` (who), `sem:Place` (where), and `sem:Time` (when). Further constraints classes `sem:Role`, `sem:Temporary` and `sem:View` can add information on the role of an actor, a temporal constraint or on a specific viewpoint respectively.

3.4. Timeline output

The final output in this demonstrator is an interactive timeline. This timeline contains ordered events extracted from Wikidata, as well as three additional components: (i) a brief description taken from Wikipedia (ii) event type information (iii) participant information. The events with no timestamps

AUGUST 10, 1792

10 AUGUST

The Insurrection of 10 August 1792 was a defining event of the French Revolution, when armed revolutionaries in Paris, increasingly in conflict with the French monarchy, stormed the Tuileries Palace. The conflict led France to abolish the monarchy and establish a republic. Conflict between King Louis XVI of France and the country's new revolutionary Legislative Assembly increased through the spring and summer of 1792 as Louis vetoed radical measures voted upon by the Assembly. Tensions accelerated dramatically on August 1 when news reached Paris that the commander of the allied Prussian and Austrian armies had issued the Brunswick Manifesto, threatening "unforgettable vengeance" on Paris should harm be done to the French Monarchy. On August 10th, the National Guard of the Paris Commune and fédérés from Marseille and Brittany stormed the King's residence in the Tuileries Palace in Paris, which was defended by the Swiss Guards. Hundreds of Swiss guardsmen and 400 revolutionaries were killed in the battle, and Louis and the royal family took shelter with the Legislative Assembly. The formal end of the monarchy occurred six weeks later on September 21st as one of the first acts of the new National Convention, which established a Republic on the next day. The insurrection and its outcomes are most commonly referred to by historians of the Revolution simply as "the 10 August"; other common designations include "the day of the 10 August" (French: *journée du 10 août*) or "the Second Revolution".

event_type

riot

actor

François Joseph Westermann

Louis XVI of France

Karl Josef von Bachmann

Augustin-Joseph de Mailly

Claude Fournier (revolutionary)

First French Republic

French First Republic

Antoine Joseph Santerre

role

commanding officer

commanding officer

commanding officer

commanding officer

combatant

combatant

commanding officer

Figure 3: Event description example for 10 August

were therefore discarded from the timeline.

Figure 3 shows one event description for the 10 August. The user can read a summary of what happened during this event, as well as some additional information retrieved from Wikidata and Wikipedia. The user therefore understands that 10 August was a riot implying different actors like Louis XVI of France as a commanding officer, or the French First Republic as a combatant. Figure 4 lastly displays the interactive timeline overview. The user can manually slide events over time and click on each of them to better understand what happened. On the bottom of the figure, one can see that it is also possible to see which events happened during a coarser period of time, like for example the Kingdom of France.

4. Conclusion

In this demonstration paper, we presented a system that is able to retrieve events and features of the French Revolution to construct a timeline of ordered events and descriptions. During this process, the user can choose how events can be selected and is walked through the different steps of the process, that makes the system transparent. The user lastly has access to an interactive timeline to better understand the series of events during the

Figure 4: Output timeline overview

French Revolution.

The system described in this paper furthermore helped to identify some first challenges for building narratives from knowledge graphs. These challenges are linked to the main steps described in Section 3: 1) collect data 2) extract features 3) build the network. The main challenge for collecting data is to assess how to best choose the set of events that optimally describe the coarser event. Should such a set contain all events that happened, or only the most relevant, or only the ones that are interesting for one user? When extracting features, there is the challenge of completing missing information, like participants or locations. What additional resources or algorithms are best to complete the narrative graph? Lastly, the challenge when building the graph network is to find or define the ontology that is best suited for the application, and to populate this ontology.

Takeaways from this paper are also about possible future work directions. One first direction could be to study the temporality of the narrative, to better understand how events unfold. In the demonstrator, the timeline output provides a sequence of events ordered in time, but it does not provide explanations for how one event might have triggered changes that in turn caused another event. One second challenge and direction is about the evaluation of the narrative. For instance, one assumption here is that Wikidata and Wikipedia contain objective non-contradictory facts, but one interesting track would be to compare different input resources, or to add confidence scores to each triple. Another direction would be to see how well the system would scale to other events such as other revolutions. Lastly, one direction could be linked to pattern identification and event forecasting, to generalise from instantiated examples.

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